

DAMAGE IN GLARE LAMINATES UNDER INDENTATION LOADS: EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

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SUMMARY

The paper presents experiments on the development of damage in the interfaces between the layers of GLARE 3-2/1-0.4. A cohesive zone model and a particular modelling technique are proposed to investigate damage onset and propagation. The numerical approach is applied to the analysis of the performed experiments with promising results.

Keywords: GLARE, denting, cohesive elements, interlaminar damage

1. INTRODUCTION

The most appealing characteristics of GLARE, a co-cured fiber metal laminate of aluminium alloy sheets and Glass/Epoxy plies, lie in the area of fatigue performance and large load carrying capability beyond the elastic range. Such characteristics have been proved under many different conditions [1, 2, 3] and indicate that GLARE laminates can be adopted to manufacture primary aircraft structures with enhanced properties of damage and impact tolerance. GLARE performances depend on a synergic collaboration between metallic and composite layers and rely, at a certain extent, on the effectiveness of load transfer mechanisms across their interfaces. These considerations highlight the importance of investigating GLARE response under those conditions that can potentially induce damage at interfaces between the constitutive layers of the laminate.

Low energy impacts are a prominent cause of this type of damage, as it is well recognized for long fiber reinforced plastics, such as in carbon/epoxy composites [4]. Although the experimental evaluation of post-impact strength is a basic issue in the field of damage tolerance, the investigation of the behavior of a laminate under low energy impact conditions is complicated by several factors. Dynamic effects, such as inertia forces, visco-elasticity and strain rate sensitivity of damage mechanisms play a not negligible role in the laminate response. Moreover, test conditions are controlled by the selected impact energy level and it is generally difficult to control the load levels applied to the laminate. Such considerations point out the advantages to study the onset and the development of damage under denting conditions, which are characterized by the quasi-static application of a concentrated indentation load and can be considered similar to low-velocity high-mass impacts [5]. Denting load conditions can be the cause

of damage development in vehicle structure and allow studying the damage evolution at well defined load levels without dynamic effects. For the same reasons, denting can also be considered to be a particularly interesting benchmark for the development and the assessment of numerical approaches to analyze and predict the development of damage at the interfaces between the constituent plies of GLARE laminates. One of the most promising approaches is the application of cohesive zone models [6,7], which has been proved effective in modeling the propagation of interlaminar damage in composite laminates in quasi-static and dynamic finite element analyses [8,9,10,11].

The paper moves from the previous considerations and proposes the application of an approach based on cohesive laws to model the onset and the development of damage at the interfaces of GLARE laminates in denting conditions. Finite element analyses carried out by means of explicit time integration scheme have been chosen to easily handle with contact conditions and possible onset of unstable crack propagations. A cohesive law has been implemented in Abaqus and has been adopted within a particular modeling technique, which is adequate to model all aspects of the interlaminar layer in GLARE laminate at a reasonable computational cost. The modeling approach will be first outlined and the advantages with respect to the choice of conventional cohesive elements will be outlined. The experimental denting and dent damage detection experiments performed on a selected type of GLARE will then be presented. In particular, the results of denting tests carried out increasing load level on a type of Glare laminate and the performed SEM analyses to identify interface damage will be reported. Finally, the application of the numerical approach to the analyses of the experiments will present the potentiality of the approach to model damage onset and development and will be used to achieve a better insight on the response of GLARE laminates loaded by a concentrated indentation force.

2. MODELLING APPROACH

2.1 Modelling approaches based on cohesive elements

The approach that has been adopted to model the onset and the propagation of damage in the interfaces of GLARE laminates is an application of cohesive zone models, that have been proposed by many authors for interlaminar damage in carbon/epoxy laminates [7,8,9,10,11,12,13]. Typically, such models are implemented in elements having zero or very small interface thickness which connect plies or sub-laminates. Figure 1-A shows an interface element between two sub-laminates during a fracture process. Elements are characterised by traction-displacement laws that link the stress transmitted through the interface, σ , to the displacement discontinuities between the adjacent surfaces, δ .

If the interface is undamaged, the element must represent a very stiff connection working in elastic range. The traction-displacement law can be reduced to the following three scalar equations between the three stress components transmitted through the interface, namely the axial stress, σ_{zz} , and the two shear stress, τ_{zx} and τ_{zy} , and the components of δ :

$$\sigma_{zz} = D_{zz} \delta_{zz} ; \tau_{zx} = D_{zx} \delta_x ; \tau_{zy} = D_{zy} \delta_y \quad (1)$$

It can be observed that components of δ can be associated to the three different possible opening modes of a fracture at the interface, δ_I , δ_{II} and δ_{III} , as expressed in Eq. 2:

$$\delta_I = \begin{cases} \delta_z & \text{if } \delta_z > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } \delta_z \leq 0 \end{cases}; \delta_{II} = \delta_x; \delta_{III} = \delta_y \quad (2)$$

A continuum damage mechanics approach can then be applied to the traction-displacement law, to model the degradation of the interface. In processes evolving according one of the three basic opening modes (I, II and III), damage onset will be detected by limit values of the discontinuities, namely δ_{I0} , δ_{II0} and δ_{III0} . Beyond such limits damage will evolve according to a prescribed law to represent the degradation of the interface. The approach presented in this work adopts the constitutive response presented in [8], which is based on the bi-linear traction-displacement response presented in Fig. 1-B. This approach also assumes that all the properties relevant to mode III are identical to the ones in mode II. Hence, the two possible opening modes are the one driven by an axial stress σ_I and the shear mode driven by the shear stress resultant, σ_{II} , defined in Fig. 1-B. In order to correctly represent the toughness of the interface, the bi-linear responses presented in Fig. 1-B fulfil the following links between the critical energy release rates and the work done during the modelled fracture process:

$$\int_0^{\infty} \sigma_I d\delta_I = G_{Ic}; \int_0^{\infty} \sigma_{II} d\delta_{II} = G_{IIc} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1 – Interface element set between two sub-laminates (A) and bi-linear response adopted in the cohesive law (B)

The strength levels of the interface directly identify the peak stress in the bi-linear responses, σ_{I0} and σ_{II0} and consequently the limit of linear elastic behaviour δ_{I0} , δ_{II0} . Equation 3 allows determining the final displacement δ_{IF} and δ_{IIIF} shown in Fig. 1-B. Hence, the bi-linear responses for processes evolving according to pure modes I or II are completely determined. Mixed mode processes are addressed by introducing a strength criterion and a toughness criterion. Algorithms for the introduction of such criteria into the constitutive law have been presented by several authors [8, 11].

2.2 Alternative modelling technique

One of the main drawbacks of the approaches based on cohesive elements is represented by the need of introducing degrees of freedom between the adjacent surfaces that actually do not exist before the onset of a fracture process. In order to avoid relative motions at the interfaces, extremely high values for the interface stiffness element are required. It is known that such stiffness can lead to numerical spurious oscillations [14] and that, on the other hand, an excessively compliant interface lead to an unrealistic

behaviour of the numerical model [13]. Several authors have proposed different ways to find the best trade-off between such numerical requirements [13,15,16]. Moreover, if an approach based on an explicit time integration scheme is adopted, as envisaged in the introduction of the present paper, the stiffness of the interface will directly affect the stable time step and lead to very high computational time costs [17]. In order to evade such difficulties, an alternative modelling technique can be proposed, based on the different roles that are actually played by the in-plane and the out-of-plane stress components acting in a laminate. Such roles can be pointed out considering a laminate in a very simple bending condition, as in Fig. 2-A. The translational equilibrium of a single lamina can be formalised as in Eq. 4, considering the membrane force per unit with, N , and the shear stress transferred through the interfaces.

$$\frac{dN_{xx}}{dx} = \tau_{xz}(z+dz) - \tau_{xz}(z) \quad (4)$$

Fig. 2 – Stress resultants acting on a single lamina in bending conditions (A) and proposed finite element scheme (B)

Fig. 3 – Fracture process described in the proposed modeling technique

In the proposed modeling technique, the area of the lamina cross section is considered lumped at the lamina mid-plane and represented by a bi-dimensional element, such as a membrane or a shell element. Such bi-dimensional elements are mutually connected by interface elements only carrying the out-of-plane stress components. Hence, conventional brick elements with a constitutive behavior characterized by a null in-plane response could be adopted as interface elements. Figure 2-B presents the resulting finite element scheme. The fracture processes are tracked by means of the vector of relative displacements between the mid-planes, Δ , which can be expressed as a function

of the displacement of the nodes, indicated as \mathbf{U}^+ and \mathbf{U}^- in Fig. 3. Moreover, within a small strain assumption, Δ , can be related to the strain state in the solid element, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$.

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \left\{ \varepsilon_{zz} \quad \gamma_{xz} \quad \gamma_{yz} \right\}^T = \Delta / t_k \quad (5)$$

If the vector of displacement discontinuities $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ is conceptually replaced by Δ , Eq. 5 can be used to convert a generic traction-displacement law, as the one described in par. 2.1, into a stress-strain law to be attributed to the solid elements, which will transmit only a out-of-plane stress components. In the elastic range, such law will be calibrated by the out-of-plane stiffness of the composite material, without requiring any penalty stiffness. A scalar damage variable is introduced to represent the degradation of stiffness properties during the evolution of a fracture process, according to the bi-linear $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ - $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ response, presented in Fig. 3, which will exactly correspond to the traction-displacement response presented in Fig. 1-B. Hence, the constitutive response attributed to the solid element will follow Eq. 6.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{zz} \\ \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} E_{zz} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & G_{xz} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{yz} \end{bmatrix} (1-d) \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{zz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The numerical evaluations presented in [10] indicate that the modeling technique is adequate to represent the quasi-static or dynamic bending behavior of laminates in the elastic range. Globally, it should be observed that the proposed approach does not introduce free surfaces that do not exist at beginning of the computation and does not require elements having infinitesimal or zero thickness. As a consequence all the material characteristics can be directly determined on the basis of physical considerations. Accordingly, the approach can be considered useful to model laminates with several interfaces, all of them representing a potential location of damage onset, and to limit the computational costs of analyses carried out by means of explicit finite element scheme.

3. EXPERIMENTAL TESTS

3.1 Considered GLARE grade and in-plane properties of constituent layers

The basic components of GLARE are aluminium and glass/epoxy composite layers. The outer layers (facings) are always made of aluminium, while composite layers are only used in the intermediate positions [1]. Unidirectional tapes of S2-Glass fibers with FM94 Cytex epoxy resins are used for the composite layers. They have $0.125 \div 0.127$ mm thickness and 59% fibre volume fraction. In this paper, attention will be focused on GLARE 3-2/1-0.4. Such a FML consists of 2 outer layer of Al 2024 – T3 with a thickness of 0.4 mm and a central composite layer made up of two S2-Glass UD plies laminated in a cross-ply fashion. Table 1 presents the in-plane properties of the constituent materials. It should be observed that the transverse stiffness of unidirectional fiberglass ply is likely to be degraded by transverse matrix cracking during the deformation process. Such effect has been recognized to be significant in determining the mean stress vs. strain response of a GLARE laminate in [19] and will be taken into account by introducing a reduced stiffness in the numerical computations.

Table 1 – in-plane properties of GLARE constituent layers

	Young Modulus (GPa)		Yield stress (MPa)		Ultimate stress (MPa)	
	L	LT	L	LT	L	LT
Al 2024-T3 – 0.4 mm	72.4	71.8	363.5	331.0	542.6	527.6
S2 Glass [0]	50.9	6.7	-	-	1626.0	19.3
S2 Glass/Cross Ply ([0][90])	25.4		-	-	769.3	

3.2 DCB tests on Glare interfaces

The toughness of GLARE interfaces plays a fundamental role in damage propagation but they can not be measured by classical test methods, such as DCB or ENF tests, directly applied to GLARE laminates. In these experimental approaches it is required that the unique dissipative mechanism that affects the test response is the propagation of interlaminar fractures [20]. This requirement can not be fulfilled by specimens just made of fibre metal laminates, at least for specimen of reasonable thickness. In fact, in bending conditions of the DCB or ENF tests, the aluminium layers of the laminate would unavoidably experience plastic deformation, with the dissipation of much more energy than that involved in the propagation of the interlaminar fracture. Such considerations lead to the measurement of interface toughness in GLARE sub-laminates bonded between 250 mm long, 25 mm wide and 4 mm thick Al 7075 T6 bars. Such type of bending stiffness reinforced specimen, shown in Fig. 4, has been employed to measure the mode I interlaminar toughness by means of DCB tests for the interfaces between the aluminium layer and the composite ply and between the glass plies of GLARE 3-2/1-0.4. Table 2 presents the results obtained by applying the area method to the DCB force vs. displacement curve.

3.3 Denting experiments on GLARE 3-2/1-0.4

Denting experiments have been carried out on GLARE 3-2/1-0.4 laminates. The specimens adopted in this study have square shape with 100 mm long edges. During the test, specimens have been clamped in a fixture, consisting of two 15 mm thick square steel plates. The two plates have been fastened by eight bolts, tightened at 40 Nm and present a circular opening of 8 cm diameter, which is the test area. The indentation has been accomplished by means of a steel indenter with a hemispherical tip and a diameter of 15 mm. The indenter was pressed against the centre of the specimen, using a 20 kN tensile-compressive machine. The test has been carried out in displacement-controlled mode, in compliance with the ASTM standard [5], with a loading and unloading rate of 1 mm/min. A series of loading-unloading tests have been performed on different laminates at increasing load level, until failure has been reached. Figure 5-A sketches the test set-up, while Fig. 5-B provides the force vs. displacement curves of 5 specimens indented at increasing load levels from 1000 N to 4500 N, showing both the loading and unloading curve. Delaminated areas in indented GLARE specimens have been assessed by means of non-destructive (ultrasonic C-scan) inspections of dented plates and destructive sectioning of the laminate through the centre of the indent followed by etching and Scanning Electron Microscopy. The purpose of this double inspection was

to get a better insight in the nature and evolution of the delamination damage and check the reliability of the C-scan against the information obtained from SEM and chemical etching. Figure 6 presents the results of SEM inspections on 3 specimens, while Fig. 7 reports the residual dent depth and the delaminated area, measured by means of C-SCAN inspections, versus the load applied in the test. Figure 5-B shows that the laminate has been plasticized even at the lowest load level and Fig. 7-A reports that the residual dent depth linearly increases with the applied load. On the other hand, delamination was observed only beyond an applied load of 2000 N (Fig. 7-B).

Fig. 4 – DCB specimen for measurement of toughness in GLARE interfaces

Table 2 – G_{Ic} values of GLARE interfaces

interface	G_{Ic} (J/m ²)	STD (J/m ²)
Al/Glass	3067	174
Glass [0]/[90]	3545	98

Fig. 5 – Denting test practice (A) and force vs. displacement results (B)

Different pattern of delamination can be observed in the specimens loaded to different load levels. The inspection techniques revealed three different type of damage developed at the interface Al/Glass (i), at the interface between the composite plies Glass[0]/[90] (ii) and at the lower interface Glass/Al (iii), respectively. The first type of damage is barely visible for the specimen tested at 2000 N, shown in Fig. 6-A, and it has developed along a circular crown in Fig. 6-B. Such figure refers to a specimen tested up to 3000 N and also shows a clear circular central delamination (ii) at the Glass[0]/[90] interface. Figure 6-C, referred to a specimen tested up to 4000 N, evidences a large circular central delamination at the lower Glass/Al interface (iii), though other minor damage can be detected in the other interfaces. It should be pointed out that from these observations in can not be concluded whether the delamination occurred during the loading or the unloading stage of the indentation. Furthermore, it should be pointed out that the onset of delamination does not lead to an abrupt or noticeable change in the slope of the load-penetration curve. Notwithstanding a certain

randomness in the development of damage patterns, a clear trend can be discerned which is shown in Fig. 7, which reports the course of delaminated area with the maximum applied load.

Fig. 6 – SEM inspections on laminates tested at 2000 N (A), 3000 N (B) and 4000 N (C)

Fig. 7 – Dent depth vs. Load (A) and Delaminated Area vs. Load (B)

4. NUMERICAL ANALYSES OF DAMAGE PROPAGATION IN GLARE INTERFACES

4.1 Application of the proposed numerical approach to DCB specimen

The previously described numerical approach has been applied to model the DCB tests performed on the bending stiffness reinforced specimen presented at par. 3.2. The Al 7075 bars have been modelled by means of continuum shell elements while the GLARE constituent layer have been modelled by bi-dimensional elements connected by solids. Connection elements have been characterised by the material law presented in section 2, which has been implemented in a VUMAT subroutine linked to the Abaqus/Explicit code [17]. The solids of the Al/Glass and Glass[0]/[90] interfaces have been characterised by the toughness values reported in Table 2. The axial strength of the interfaces, σ_{I0} , has been initially set to 25 MPa. Figure 8-A shows the model of the DCB test which includes the load application hinges, modelled by two rigid bodies (dark elements in Fig. 8-A) pinned to two reference node. One of the nodes has been kept fixed, while a smoothly increasing velocity has been attributed to other one in order to perform a quasi-static analysis. Figures 8-B and 8-C show the model before and during crack propagation, respectively. Figure 9 presents the numerical-experimental correlations referred to a DCB test carried out with an initial pre-crack in the Glass [0]/[90] interface. Correlation has been significantly improved by increasing the axial strength of such interface, σ_{I0} , from 25 MPa to 35 MPa. Figure 10-A indicates that the Al/Glass interfaces, which have a lower toughness of the initially pre-cracked Glass[0]/[90] interface, are partially damaged during the crack propagation in the analyses with $\sigma_{I0} = 25$. If the strength of Glass[0]/[90] interface is increased to 35 MPa and all the other parameters are kept fixed, the lower Al/Glass interface turns out to be completely damaged (Fig. 10-B). Such phenomenon explains the increment of the

overall energy and force levels required to open the crack, reported in the force vs. displacement response. As a matter of fact, the experimental evidence reported in Fig. 10-C confirms that the crack opening process also involves damage in all the Al/Glass interfaces, fibre bridging and in-plane damage of composite plies as well.

Fig. 8 – Numerical model of a DCB test

Fig. 9 – Numerical-experimental correlation of DCB test

Fig. 10 – Numerical and experimental damage at the crack tip in the DCB test

Fig. 11 – Developed model of the indentation test on GLARE 3-2/1-0.4

Hence, the analyses of DCB tests indicate that a cohesive zone model, which inherently models a local process characterised by a constant toughness with crack length, could provide a conservative estimation of the force levels required to open a crack in GLARE laminates. Additional dissipative mechanisms, such as the concurrent crack opening

shown in Fig. 10-B or in-plane damage of composite plies, should be considered to accurately model the phenomena occurring during damage propagation in the interfaces.

4.2 Analyses of denting experiments

Figures 11-A and 11-B show the model developed to analyse the indentation experiments carried out on GLARE laminates. Continuum shell elements have been used to model the 0.4 mm thick aluminium layers. An isotropic elastic-plastic material model associated to Von Mises yield criterion has been adopted for the metallic layers. Membrane elements have been employed for composite plies and characterised as purely elastic. The orthotropic material model has been calibrated by using the data reported in Tab. 1, though the transverse Young modulus has been reduced to 2 GPa in order to roughly take into consideration transverse matrix cracking phenomena. The interfaces have been modelled by solid elements as in the analyses of DCB tests. Mode II toughness has been set equal to toughness measured in Mode I. The disk has been constrained at the edges and a rigid analytical surface has been included in the model to represent the indenter, set in contact with the upper surface of the fibre metal laminate.

Table 3 – Loads corresponding to the numerical onset of delamination in the upper Al/Glass interface

	$\sigma_{I0} = 10$	$\sigma_{I0} = 20$	$\sigma_{I0} = 30$
$\sigma_{II0} = 40$	1110 N	1484 N	1484 N
$\sigma_{II0} = 50$	1484 N	1870 N	1870 N
$\sigma_{II0} = 80$	3002 N	-	-

Fig. 12 – Numerical-experimental correlation of indentation test at 4000 N

Fig. 13 – Delamination in the analysis with $\sigma_{I0} = 10$ MPa and $\sigma_{II0} = 80$ MPa (A) and $\sigma_{I0} = 20$ MPa and $\sigma_{II0} = 50$ MPa (B)

A loading-unloading cycle characterised by a maximum force of 4000 N has been first taken into consideration and a series of analyses have been carried out at different interlaminar strength levels. A smoothed velocity time history has been attributed to the indenter to reproduce the experimental displacement time history. Identical values of σ_{I0} and σ_{II0} have been attributed to all the interfaces in the modelled laminate. Table 3 presents the numerical evaluation matrix and the load levels corresponding to the development of damage in the loading phase of the analysis. In such a phase, damage always occurred in the upper Al/Glass interface and the reported loads correspond to the occurrence of damage level beyond the 0.90 threshold. Loads at damage onset appear greatly influenced by the interlaminar strength, particularly by σ_{II0} . Basing on the linear trend shown in Fig. 7-B, the experimental load level at the onset of interlaminar damage can be estimated at about 1750 N ÷ 2000 N, so that a value of 50 MPa can be identified for the interlaminar strength σ_{II0} . Figure 12 reports the numerical load-penetration curves of three analyses carried out in this sensitivity study. Results show that the correlation with the experimental curve is appreciable and that numerical curves are not affected by the development of delamination. Figure 13-A reports the evolution of delamination in the analysis carried out with $\sigma_{I0} = 10$ MPa and $\sigma_{II0} = 80$ MPa. Delamination at the upper Al/Glass interface develops along a circular crown, at about 3000 N. The lower Al/Glass interface also delaminates during the unloading phase. The final state is in good qualitative agreement with the experimental one presented in Fig. 6-B. Figure 13-B is referred to another analysis, carried out with $\sigma_{I0} = 20$ MPa and $\sigma_{II0} = 50$ MPa. Delamination at the upper interface occurs at about 1900 N and develops over a circular central zone. During unloading, the lower Al/Glass interface delaminates as well, though damage appear less severe than in the case considered in Fig. 13-A. Globally, the analyses of all numerical results indicate that the upper Al/Glass interface tends to exhibit a mode II delamination during the loading phase of the test, while the lower interface can undergo a delamination process in mode I during unloading. Damage during unloading is eliminated if the interlaminar axial strength, σ_{I0} , is raised at 30 MPa.

Fig. 14 – Numerical-experimental correlation of indentation tests at different load levels

Fig. 15 – Numerical vs. experimental delaminated area at different load levels

The model with $\sigma_{I0} = 20$ MPa and $\sigma_{II0} = 50$ MPa provides the best correlation among the ones included in the numerical evaluation matrix and it has been adopted to perform analyses at different load levels. The load-penetration curves reported in Fig. 14 indicate that the correlation of load-penetration curves and of dent depths at the end of the tests is appreciable. Damage onset is in agreement with the experimental data, but the evolution of delaminated area with the applied load, presented in Fig. 15, shows significant discrepancies with respect to the experiments. The model predicts a rapid propagation of damage after the onset load, while experimental tests have shown a more progressive increment of delaminated area with the applied load. Such discrepancy could be explained considering the poor mesh refinement adopted, taking the fracture toughness for crack initiation to be the same as for crack propagation and the difficulties to model complex damage phenomena, as pointed in the analyses of DCB tests.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Experimental and numerical approaches have been proposed to investigate the development of damage in GLARE interfaces. The performed denting experiments, carried out at different load level on the most studied GLARE variant (GLARE 3-2/1-04), allowed tracking the evolution of the permanent dent depth and of delamination at the interfaces with the applied load. It has been observed that delamination occurs without any noticeable modification in the global load-penetration response. The experiments have been then modelled by applying a numerical approach based on the introduction of a cohesive zone model in a particular modelling technique, suitable to be adopted in explicit finite element codes. Considering DCB tests, the approach proved its capability to represent the propagation of cracks at the interfaces of GLARE laminates and results have also pointed out the possible role played by concurrent damage mechanisms in the test response. The application of the approach to the analyses of denting experiments has been carried out with a relatively coarse finite element scheme and identical strength levels attributed to all the interfaces. Notwithstanding such limitations, the developed model proved to be quite effective to represent the delamination process occurred in the tests. The numerical approach allowed determining the main delamination modes and confirmed that damage develops at the interfaces without affecting the load-penetration curve. It also provided a strong indication regarding the development of damage during the unloading phase of the experiments.

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